

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

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In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

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CHAYON ZAHARIDAN DORI VOSITASI SIFATIDA FOYDALANISH

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Annotatsiya: *Scorpiones* – chayonlar o'rgimchaksimonlar turkumi vakili, ba'zan mustaqil sinf sifatida qaraladi. Chayon va uning zahari Xitoy, Osiyo, Hindiston va Afrika mamlakatlarida ming yillar davomida an'anaviy tibbiyotda qo'llanilgan. Chayon zaharida tuzlar, nukleotidlar, biogen aminlar, fermentlar, mukoproteinlar, shuningdek, peptidlar va oqsillar (masalan, neyrotoksinlar) mavjud. Chayon zahari biologik xususiyatlari yaqindan o'rganilganda uning turli xil kasalliklar, yallig'lanishlarni, shu jumladan, saraton o'sishini kamaytirishi, apoptozni qo'zg'atishi, saraton rivojlanishini va metastazni ingibir qilishi aniqlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: *Scorpiones*, mukopolisaxaridlar, mukoproteinlar, gistamin, serotonin, geterotsiklik komponentlar, apoptoz, Bangalin, glioma, leykemiya, neyroblastoma, limfoma, pankreatit, siklin D1.

Chayonlar (*Scorpiones*) - o'rgimchaksimonlar sinfiga mansub qadimiy va qiziqarli hayvonlardir. Ular asosan issiq va quruq iqlimli hududlarda, jumladan, O'zbekistonda ham keng tarqalgan. Hozirda dunyoda 750 dan ortiq turi ma'lum, O'zbekistonda esa ularning bir nechtasi, xususan chipor chayon (*Mesobuthus eupeus*) keng uchraydi. Chayon tanasi boshko'krak va qorin bo'limidan iborat. Ularning tanasi 1 sm dan 20 sm gacha uzunlikda bo'lishi mumkin. Boshko'krak qismi qattiq qalqon bilan qoplangan bo'lib, markazida bir juft katta va ikki yonida bir nechta kichik ko'zlari bor. Tanasi usti xitin qobiq bilan qoplangan bo'lib, bu qobiqning ustki qismida mum qatlami mavjud - bu chayonni qurib ketishdan himoya qiladi. Qorin qismi ikki bo'limga bo'linadi: oldingi qismi kengroq, orqa qismi esa ingichka va egiluvchan bo'lib, dum shaklida orqaga bukiladi. Dumi oxirida joylashgan nashtar (teshuvchi igna) ichida zahar bezlari bor. Chayonlar bu nashtar orqali o'lja yoki dushmaniga zahar yuboradi. Oldingi oyoqlari yirik qisqichlarga aylangan bo'lib, ular yordamida o'lja ushlanadi. Nafas olish esa maxsus kitobcha o'pka organlari orqali sodir bo'ladi. Chayonlar kechasi faol bo'ladi, ya'ni tungi yirtqichlar hisoblanadi. Ular hasharotlar va boshqa mayda hayvonlar bilan oziqlanadi. Ular spermatoforlar yordamida ko'payadi, va ko'pchilik turlari tirik tug'adi – yosh chayonlar tug'ilgach, bir necha kun onasining orqasida yurishadi. Chayon chaqqanida odatda kuchli og'riq, qizarish va shish kuzatiladi. O'zbekiston hududidagi turlar odatda inson hayoti uchun xavfli emas, biroq chaqilganda ehtiyot choralarini ko'rish lozim[1].

Chayonlar zahari tufayli ilon va boshqa zaharli hayvonlar kabi juda ko'p o'rganilgan. Chayon chaqishi turli allergik reaksiyalar keltirib chiqarishi, buyrak va

qon tomirlariga, asab tizimiga ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin. Ammo shu bilan birga foydali jihatlari ham mavjud. Chayon zahari tarkibida suv, shilliq qavat, past molekulyar og'irlikdagi peptid, ferment, erkin aminokislotalar, biogen amin, nukleotid, mukopolisaxaridlar, mukoproteinlar, gistamin, serotonin, geterotsiklik komponentlar va bir nechta noma'lum moddalar aralashmasi mavjud. Zahar tarkibi o'rganilganda uning turli xil yallig'lanish va mikrobiologik kasalliklarni, shu jumladan, saraton o'sishini kamaytirishi, apoptozni qo'zg'atishi, saraton rivojlanishini va metastazni ingibir qilishi aniqlangan. Bundan tashqari Xitoy, Afrika, Hindiston, Osiyo mamlakatlarida oqsilga boy ozuqa sifatida iste'mol qilinadi[2,3]. Chayon zahari Xitoyda turli oziq ovqat va dori vositalariga qo'shib qo'llaniladi. Bunday preparatlardan foydalanilganda diabetni davolash holatlari kuzatilgan. Tadqiqotlarda chayon zahari tarkibidagi oqsillar oshqozon ostibezi langergans orolchalaridagi beta hujayralarini faollashtirgani va ularning ta'sirini, ishlash faoliyati yaxshilangani aniqlangan. Chayon zahari tarkibidagi peptidlar beta hujayralarining ko'payishiga ham ta'sir etgani aniqlangan 1-jadval [2].

1-jadval

Chayon zaharining dori vositasi sifatida qo'llanilishi bo'yicha statistik tahlil

Yo'nalish	Chayon zaharining ta'siri	Tadqiqotlar va Qo'llanilish
Saratonni davolash	O'simta hujayralarini sekinlashtirish, metastazni ingibir qilish	Glioma, leykemiya, neyroblastoma, limfoma
Diabetni davolash	Beta hujayralarining faollashuvi, insulin ishlab chiqarish	Xitoyda diabetga qarshi qo'llaniladi
Neyrodegenerativ kasalliklar (Alzheimer, Parkinson)	Neyroprotektiv ta'sir	Hayvonlar tajribasi
Yallig'lanish kasalliklari	Yallig'lanishni kamaytirish, mikrobiologik ta'sir	Yallig'lanishning oldini olish

Tarixan chayon zahari turli kasalliklarni davolash uchun ishlatilgan. Misol uchun, chayon yog'i o'simta hujayralari, infeksiyalar va yallig'lanishga qarshi kurashda qo'llaniladi. Chayonning o'zini ham spirtli eritmaga solib qo'yilganda tarkibidagi zahar va oqsillar eritmaga chiqib spirtni boyitadi. Bundan qo'l va oyoq bog'im og'riqlarida foydalaniladi. Ta'kidlash joizki, odam zaharlanganda, uning avtonom nerv tizimi ta'sirlanadi, natijada insulin darajasi ko'tariladi va glyukagon, kortizol va angiotensin II kabi gormonlar chiqariladi [4]. Zahar tarkibidagi komponentlar chayonlarga o'zini himoya qilishda va o'ljasini tutishda hal qiluvchi rol o'ynaydi. So'nggi tadqiqotlar va eksperimental tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, xom chayon zahari, o'ziga xos izolyatsiyalangan oqsillar va peptidlar saratonning

muhim xususiyatlariga xalaqit berishi mumkin, bu laboratoriya sharoitlarida va tirik organizmlarda samarali ekanligini isbotlangan. Chayon zaharidan olingan BmBKTx o'simtani bostiruvchi p53 oqsilining parchalanishini bostiradi. Chayon zaharidan ajratilgan yana bir peptid - bu "Bangalin". U937 (gistotsitik limfoma) va K562 (xoronik miyelogen leykemiya) inson leykemiya hujayralarining o'sishini sekinlashtiradi va ularni apoptozga aylantiradi. Bengalin mitoxondriyal o'lim kaskadlariga vositachilik qilib, leykemiya hujayralariga qarshi halokatli mexanizm ta'minlaydi. Bangalin ayollarda osteoporozni davolash uchun ham ishlatiladi[4,5]. Tadqiqotlar glioma, leykemiya, neyroblastoma va limfoma, o'pka, ko'krak, jigar, oshqozon osti bezi va prostata saratoni kabi qator saratonlarni davolashda chayon zahari samaradorligini o'rganilgan. Chayon zaharining saratonga va boshqa kasalliklarga qarshi xususiyatlari ma'lum tozalangan toksinlar bilan bog'liq[4,6].

Misol uchun chayon zahari komponenti III (SVC III) inson leykemiyaga qarshi tanlab ta'sir qiladi. Chayon zahari komponenti SVC III hujayra siklini to'xtatadi va siklin D1 oqsili ishlab chiqarishni bostirish orqali G1 fazasida hujayra proliferatsiyasini ingibir qiladi. Pankreatit - oshqozon osti bezi va uning atrofidagi to'qimalarning shishishi. Bu oshqozon osti bezi fermentlarining pufakchalar orqali oqishi tufayli yuzaga keladi. Ushbu pufakchalarda yallig'lanishni keltirib chiqaradigan oqsilli fermentlar mavjud. Vesikulalar hujayra membranasini ochishga, oqsillarni chiqarishga va hujayra tarkibining qolgan qismiga ta'sir qilmasdan ularni tashishga imkon beradi. Ushbu oqsillar vesikulyar assotsiatsiyalangan membrana oqsillari yoki VAMPlar deb ataladi. Chayon zahari ushbu VAMPlarni samarali ravishda sindirishi va vesikulalarning oqsillarni chiqarish va ularni tashish qobiliyatini yo'qotishi kuzatiladi [6].

Xulosa: Chayon zahari tarkibidagi peptidlar turli xil saraton, infeksiyali yallig'lanish kasalliklari uchun juda samarali. Chayon zaharining bunday foydali tomonlardan kelib chiqib biz chayonni sanoat miqyosida ko'paytirib, chayon plantatsiyalari yaratishimiz, uning zaharidan yanada keng miqyosda foydalanishimiz lozim. Dori vositalariga qo'shish va dori sifatida foydalanishni chuqurroq o'rganishimiz kerak.

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